

AVAILABILITY AND HELPFULNESS OF LOW VISION ASSISTIVE DEVICES FOR LOW VISION LEARNERS ATTENDING INCLUSIVE SCHOOLS IN KAKAMEGA COUNTY, KENYA.

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ABSTRACT

Purpose:

This study aimed at investigating the use of low vision assistive devices among low vision learners attending inclusive schools in Kakamega County.

Methods

A census survey identified 21 low vision learners who had been assessed and placed in 11 primary public inclusive schools in Kakamega County. Participants responded to the LV Prasad Functional Vision Questionnaire, which elicited how their vision influences their ease of functioning in day to day activities. They were further guided to respond to whether or not they had assistive devices and if these were helping them. Data was entered into SPSS version 25 software and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Data was summarized and presented using tables, figures and percentages.

Results

The results showed that the majority (63.2%) did not have assistive devices, which may have resulted in the poor performance in activities of daily living among the participants. Available assistive devices included: spectacle magnifiers (15.8%), dome magnifiers (5.3%), telescope (5.3%) and spectacles (5.3%). One learner (5.3%) reported use of multiple assistive devices. Only one learner reported that their assistive device was serving them perfectly well. The findings of this study bridged the knowledge gap in the lack of assistive devices as a key barrier to effective implementation of the inclusive learning system in Kenya.

Conclusion

The majority of low vision learners attending inclusive schools in Kakamega County did not use any assistive devices and of the few who use them, most of them report that the devices are not serving them well.

INTRODUCTION

Low vision (LV) forms part of visual impairment and is defined as patients who have a visual acuity of less than 6/18 to 3/60 in the better eye or a visual field of less than 10 degrees from the point of fixation after best correction with spectacles or medication.¹ Studies have established that low vision lowers the quality of life of the affected patients². Furthermore, visual loss has an economic impact on the lives of the affected individuals, their families and society at large³. Low vision not only affects the family in terms of their role towards the affected person but also their psychological state of mind where they have to adjust their lives to fit the responsibilities of taking care of a low vision family member⁴.

Rehabilitation services and administration of assistive devices improve the quality of life of low vision patients⁵. These services not only improve the visual functioning but also the social functioning of the low vision patient⁶. Low vision services also result in patient satisfaction⁷ They also improve the quality of life of low vision patients⁸. Low vision patients have displayed poor adaptation to technology changes due to poor training⁹.

Low vision optical devices and rehabilitation services have brought a remarkable improvement in the reading performance of low vision learners¹⁰. There is also a huge improvement in the visual functioning and social functioning of low vision patients brought about by use of optical low vision assistive devices⁶. While providing these devices is helpful, it is very important to assess their effectiveness in serving the purpose for which they were meant¹¹. Despite the huge benefit that comes with use of low vision services, these services are underutilized in developing countries especially among the elderly and women¹². In schools, underutilization of low vision devices is mainly caused by lack of knowledge on how to use these devices as well as lack of follow-up by eye-care practitioners to check on the suitability of the devices¹³.

Integration of low vision services into other disciplines increases the quality of life of low vision patients¹⁴. Occupational therapy plays an important role in rehabilitation of low vision patients¹⁵. Provision of visual aids significantly increases the reading speed of low vision children¹⁶.

This tells the importance of providing low vision devices to low vision learners while they get integrated into mainstream schools. Low vision care improves the reading performance of children with multiple disabilities ¹⁰. Use of Low Vision assistive devices improves the quality of life of children with visual impairment ⁶. Optical devices also positively improve the quality of life of children with low vision ^{17,18}. Low vision devices provide good rehabilitation on low vision patients thus improving their quality of life ¹⁹. Patients undertaking rehabilitation services have experienced improved visual function, patient satisfaction and a higher quality of life ². However, some low vision patients do not understand what the Low Vision Assistive Devices (LVAS) do in helping them and would not like to identify with vision loss ²⁰. It is therefore important that low vision patients undergo guidance and counselling for them to accept their condition and the management required.

Patients who have defective color vision can benefit from glasses which have red, amber and green strips for recognition of traffic light signal and glasses with red, blue and green strips for desktop color differentiation ²¹. Software development has also made easy learning for low vision and blind learners ²². Technology has made it possible to convert input from the keyboard to braille and even translate to Arabic language ²³. Low vision and blind learners enjoy learning drawing, handwriting and signature using a computer ²⁴. However, these strategies usually allow learners utilize other senses and do not exercise their sense of sight. For learners, optical assistive devices like hand held magnifiers yield great results when used after the learners have undergone training for the same ²⁵. This implies that provision of optical devices without proper training of users may not be effective.

While many factors have been identified as hindering placement of disabled learners, including visually impaired learners into mainstream schools, the visual performance aspect of it has been underexplored. More emphasis has been placed on assessing the psycho-social aspects of life. Most of the causes of dropouts mentioned include: Stigmatization, Inappropriate curricula, poorly equipped institutions of learning and insufficiently trained teachers. This study sought to find out if there are assistive devices for low vision learners in inclusive schools, lack of which could lead to their inability to undertake tasks that are vision demanding at school hence hinder the successful implementation of inclusive education and a result, learners end up dropping out of school.

There are barriers to provision of these low vision services such as unawareness, lack of training and unavailability of the devices themselves ²⁶. Furthermore, in the United States of America, there are few optometrists who practice low vision rehabilitation and this becomes an inconvenience to the population seeking low vision services ²⁷. There is need to measure the effectiveness of each assistive device that is given to low vision patients ¹¹. This will be very helpful since visual performance in regard to tasks being undertaken by low vision learners differs and their needs vary widely from one person to another.

METHODS

Study Design

This study employed a school-based cross sectional descriptive study design.

Setting and study population

The study was conducted in public primary inclusive schools which host low vision learners in Kakamega County, Kenya. Most low vision learners attend special schools for the visually impaired and all the low vision learners in inclusive schools in Kakamega County, aged 10 to 21 years, formed the study population for this research (Visual acuity of less than 6/18 in the better eye up to 3/60 or a visual field of less than 10 degrees from the point of fixation after best correction). Out of the 76 inclusive schools in which visually impaired learners are hosted in Kakamega County, there are 11 schools in which typical low vision learners are placed by the County Educational Assessment and Resource Center.

Learners with multiple disabilities were excluded from the study. This is because some disabilities like autism affect the learners' cognitive reasoning and independent response and could affect how they respond to the Functional Vision Assessment Questionnaire. Low vision learners below 10 years were also excluded from this study because they would not be able to respond effectively to the questionnaire. Furthermore, learners whose parents didn't give their assent or consent and learners with incompletely filled out questionnaires were excluded from this study.

Data collection

Prior to the collection of data, permission was sought from the heads of the schools in which the study was conducted. An informed consent form was administered to the low vision learners who were above 18 years old prior to data collection. Similarly, guardians of learners who were below eighteen years of age were given the same forms to sign on their behalf. Assessment of visual acuity was done to classify the participants as per the WHO classification of low vision.

The LV Prasad Functional Vision Assessment (FVA) questionnaire was adopted and administered to the learners who were assisted so they may fill out before other clinical tests were conducted. The researcher guided the learners on how to fill out the questionnaire and allowed them to make their own decision. After getting their feedback, the researcher would guide them where to tick against their responses. The available low vision assistive devices were checked and classified as optical or non-optical devices and as per the tasks for which they are relevant. This was recorded against the actual tasks for which low vision learners are using this devices and compare to see whether the available devices were being used for the right tasks. Learners who were using low vision devices were asked to demonstrate how they used these devices hence assess whether or not the devices were being used in the right manner. Learners were further asked to report whether or not the assistive devices were serving them sufficiently well.

Data analysis

The data collected in the research was entered into Microsoft Excel, edited, coded and thereafter the cleaned and verified data was transferred into the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) (version 25) software. Dependent and independent variables were derived and data was analyzed using descriptive statistics; percentages and presented using bar graphs and charts.

Ethical considerations

Ethical approval to conduct the research was obtained from the Institutional Review and Ethics Committee (IREC) of Masinde Muliro University of Science and Technology (MMUST/IERC/113/2020). Furthermore, a research permit was obtained from the National Commission of Science and Technology (NACOSTI) (Reference number: 523567). The researcher adhered to all the ethical protocols established by the institution and all data obtained was protected on a password-controlled computer so that only the researcher would have access to it. Data was stored as per the university archiving policy.

RESULTS

The use assistive devices by low vision learners

Most of the learners (63.2%) do not use assistive devices while only 36.8% use assistive devices. Only 7 out of 19 low vision learners use assistive devices (Figure 1).

Figure 1: The use assistive devices by low vision learners

Type of low vision devices used by the learners in inclusive school

The researcher assessed the types of low vision devices used by learners in inclusive schools and majority (15.8%) spectacle magnifier, while the rest of the types of assistive devices represented 5.3% of the total participants using assistive devices. The results are represented in table below

Type of low vision assistive devices used by the low vision learners	Response	n	%
	A dome magnifier	1	5.3
	Not applicable	12	63.2
	Spectacle Magnifier	3	15.8
	Spectacle Magnifier, Telescope and Reading stand	1	5.3

	Spectacles	1	5.3
	Telescope	1	5.3
	Total	19	100

Table 1: Type of low vision devices used by the learners in inclusive school

Helpfulness of assistive devices to learners with low vision

Most of the learners (15.80%) who use assistive devices reported that the devices were helping them well, 10.5% reported that they were helping them a little bit, 5.3 reported that they were helping very well. However, 5.30% reported that they were not helping them at all. This creates a general need of providing the right assistive devices to address the purpose for which each is meant (Figure 2).

Figure 2 Helpfulness of assistive devices to learners with low vision

Barriers to the use of assistive devices by learners with low vision in inclusive schools

Learners who were not using low vision assistive devices highlighted various challenges to acquisition of these devices. These included high cost (10.5%), inaccessibility (15.8%), lack of awareness (10.6%), never visited an eye hospital (15.8%) and failure to be guided on the need of the devices (10.5%). The remaining 36.8% of learners were already using assistive devices.

Barriers to use of	Response	n	%
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assistive devices	High cost	2	10.5
	Inaccessibility	3	15.8
	Lack of awareness	2	10.6
	Not applicable to me	7	36.8
	Never visited an eye hospital	3	15.8
	Was told he doesn't need devices	2	10.5

Table 2: Barriers to the use of assistive devices by learners with low vision in inclusive schools

Association between demographics characteristics and use of assistive devices

A Pearson chi square was done to determine if age, gender, grade and duration of impairment is associated with the use of assistive devices among learners. The results showed that all the demographics had an insignificant association with use of assistive devices ($p > 0.05$)

Demographics	Chi square value	Significance level
Age	8.26	0.509
Gender	0.046	0.682
Grade	3.96	0.829
Duration of impairment (years)	7.27	0.400

Dependent variable: Use of assistive devices

Table 3: Association between demographics characteristics and use of assistive devices

DISCUSSION

Availability of assistive devices

This study found out that only 36.8% of the low vision learners attending inclusive school system in Kakamega County have acquired low vision assistive devices while 63.2% do not use any low vision assistive device. This creates a serious concern since it has been established that provision of low vision services and devices greatly increases the quality of life of low vision patients ². Provision of low vision assistive devices also enables low vision learners to utilize

their residual vision so that they don't have to necessarily learn braille ²⁸. Furthermore, low vision assistive devices are a good means of improving the reading rehabilitation in low vision patients ¹⁹ and their reading performance increases with magnification ^{29; 10; 6}. That means that by failing to get access to low vision assistive devices, the quality of life of these learners is greatly decreased. Some of the barriers to uptake of these devices, which have been identified from this study, include high cost of the devices, inaccessibility to the eye clinic, and unawareness of the availability of the devices. Although studies have presented the challenges facing the implementation of inclusive school systems ^{26; 30; 31}, there is a dearth of data addressing the barriers to uptake of low vision assistive devices by low vision learners in inclusive schools in Kenya. These barriers are very synonymous with what other studies have presented in the past.

Type and helpfulness of low vision assistive devices

The type of devices used by the low vision learners included mostly spectacle magnifiers. Head mounted assistive devices like spectacle magnifiers yield better results in improving visual ability and face recognition ³². Other devices included telescopes and dome magnifiers. Most of the learners reported some deficiency in the effectiveness of the assistive devices while only 5.3% reported that the device was serving perfectly well. These results agree with ¹¹, who sited the importance of assessing the effectiveness of assistive devices in order to ensure they effectively serve the purpose for which they are meant. These findings imply that most of the low vision assistive devices are not correctly serving the visual demands. For instance, some learners are only using telescopes, which only improve their distance tasks but not near tasks ³³. As a result, these learners are still likely to perform poorly in near tasks like reading despite having assistive devices. It has further been elicited that dome-shaped magnifiers do better than cylindrical-shaped magnifiers and should preferably be administered to visually impaired children ³⁴ yet only one low vision learner in this study was using a dome magnifier. Stand magnifiers have been commented for use by low vision children since they are efficient ³⁵.

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